

STRENGTH DEGRADATION IN TITANIUM MATRIX COMPOSITES EXPOSED TO FATIGUE AT ELEVATED TEMPERATURE

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SUMMARY: The residual strength of both unidirectional and cross-ply titanium matrix composites are examined after being exposed to isothermal fatigue loading at elevated temperature (427°C). The SCS6/Ti-15-3 composite system was tested with a cyclic fatigue load at 900 MPa maximum stress for the unidirectional layup and at 450 and 300 MPa for the cross-ply layup. Triangular waveforms with a minimum to maximum stress ratio of 0.05 and frequencies of 5 or 10 Hz were used. For the present conditions, the reduction in strength was not significant until after 50% of the expected life. The macroscopic behavior suggests damage accumulation consistent with fiber bridged matrix cracks. Microscopic evaluation of the failed specimens further corroborate this conclusion.

KEYWORDS: residual strength, failure of composites, fatigue, damage, failure mechanisms, fatigue life, titanium matrix composites, metal matrix composites

INTRODUCTION

Various fatigue studies of titanium matrix composites have been accomplished in recent years [1-4]. The long term goal of these and many other such studies have been to develop fatigue life maps for material characterization; thereby providing means for prediction of component design life. However, equally important to the designer is the remaining or residual strength of the material at any given fraction of the fatigue life. The present study examines the residual strength of both unidirectional and cross-ply titanium matrix composites after being exposed to isothermal fatigue loading at elevated temperature.

Damage accumulation during fatigue is expected to have a detrimental effect on the residual strength. This damage consists of the accumulation and distribution of matrix cracks, fiber cracks, and interfacial debonding. Some analytical studies have attempted to characterize the strength of metal matrix composites (MMCs) based on the distribution of constituent damage [5-6]. These investigations have focused on the fiber strength distribution and the interfacial characteristics as the critical parameters controlling the strength of the composite. Such methods have proven reliable for predicting the ultimate strength of virgin material [6]. However, in fatigue damaged specimens, it is possible the main source of damage is matrix cracking. If the fibers bridge these matrix cracks, then any significant reduction in strength may be prevented. However, there is a lack of such information. The present study investigates this important area.

MATERIAL AND EXPERIMENT DESCRIPTION

The material investigated in this study was a titanium matrix composite (TMC) composed of a titanium alloy (Ti-15V-3Cr-3Sn-3Al) continuously reinforced with silicon carbide fibers (SCS-6) at approximately 35 % fiber volume fraction. After consolidation and machining, the specimens were heat treated at 700°C in an argon environment for 24 hours. Both unidirectional, $[0]_8$, and cross-ply, $[0/90]_{2S}$, layups were considered in the present study and fatigued isothermally at 427°C. All specimens possessed a nominal length of 15 cm and width of 0.9 cm. The cross-ply specimens were rectangular coupons while the unidirectional specimens were machined with a dogbone geometry (shoulder radius: 116 cm) to ensure failure within the gauge length.

The experiments consisted of both monotonic and fatigue loading. Some specimens were fatigued to failure while others were stopped at different intervals of their fatigue life and then loaded to failure monotonically to obtain the residual strength. In addition, a few virgin specimens were loaded monotonically to failure (no prior fatigue) to obtain the ultimate strength. The unidirectional specimens were fatigued at a maximum stress of 900 MPa while two maximum stress levels, 300 MPa and 450 MPa, were used with the cross-ply specimens. A 10 Hz frequency triangular waveform with a minimum to maximum load ratio of 0.05 was chosen as the baseline cycle. However, due to extensometer slip at this frequency, the cross-ply tests at 300 MPa maximum stress were performed at 5 Hz. The monotonic tests to failure were loaded at 15 MPa/s. All tests were performed under load-control mode.

The specimen temperature within the gauge length was maintained at 427°C through the use of two 1000 W parabolic strip lamps positioned on either side (front and back) of the specimen face. Three thermocouples were welded onto the specimen within the gauge region (one in the center of the gauge length and two on either side) to monitor the specimen temperature during the test and provide input to the lamp controller. All specimens possessed a 1.27 cm gauge length and the displacement within this was obtained from a quartz rod extensometer positioned on the side of the specimen.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The static, fatigue, and residual strength data is presented in Table 1. In some cases, such as the cross-ply specimen with a 663 MPa residual strength, extensometer slip prevented the strain data from being accurately recorded. Therefore, the strain and modulus data for these cases does not appear in the table. In addition, the static tests to measure ultimate strength and the fatigue tests to obtain the fatigue life are indicated with appropriate footnotes.

Comparison of the residual strength with other parameters listed in the table such as the change in maximum strain and modulus provides some qualitative relations. For instance, an increase in the maximum strain and a decrease in the modulus correlates to a reduction in the residual strength. However, these general trends do not provide a direct quantitative relation for the strength degradation. Also, for a given load level and layup the strength degradation with cycles demonstrates significant scatter, but this is consistent with the fatigue life which displays a factor of two variation in repeated tests as seen with the cross-ply 300 MPa maximum stress experiments.

Table 1. Static, Fatigue, and Residual Strength Test Results for Unidirectional and Cross-Ply Composite Layups of SCS6/Ti-15-3 at 427°C

Layup	σ_{\max} (MPa)	Last Cycle	$\Delta\epsilon_{\max}$ (%)	ΔE (GPa)	σ_{RS} (MPa)
[0] ₈	--	--	--	--	1,386*
[0] ₈	900	7,645	0.002	- 0.2	1,325
[0] ₈	900	15,284	0.014	- 1.6	1,287
[0] ₈	900	20,244	0.109	- 4.0	900**
[0] ₈	900	30,561	--	--	900**
[0/90] _{2S}	--	--	--	--	996*
[0/90] _{2S}	--	--	--	--	844*
[0/90] _{2S}	450	6,598	0.049	- 1.0	768
[0/90] _{2S}	450	8,004	0.021	- 1.0	859
[0/90] _{2S}	450	10,692	--	--	663
[0/90] _{2S}	450	17,023	0.101	- 16.0	450**
[0/90] _{2S}	300	50,010	0.071	- 5.5	767
[0/90] _{2S}	300	80,009	0.081	- 5.0	512
[0/90] _{2S}	300	94,153	--	--	300**
[0/90] _{2S}	300	100,011	0.084	- 13.0	481
[0/90] _{2S}	300	186,003	0.103	- 19.0	300**

* Static Test to Failure

** Fatigue Test to Failure

$\Delta\epsilon_{\max}$: Difference of the maximum strain in the last recorded cycle and the first cycle

ΔE : Difference of the modulus in the last recorded cycle and the first cycle

σ_{RS} : Specimen residual strength

Figures 1 through 3 plot the residual strength versus cycles for the three conditions investigated in this study. Figure 1 presents the unidirectional data while Figures 2 and 3 present the cross ply data. The unidirectional test to 20,244 cycles and the cross-ply 300 MPa maximum stress test to 94,153 cycles each failed in fatigue before they reached their respective target cycle for residual strength determination. These points provide some indication of the scatter in the fatigue life for this material.

The unidirectional data displays a slight drop-off in the strength of approximately ten percent over the first half to two-thirds of the projected fatigue life. The majority of the strength reduction occurs near the end of the life. In fact, it is difficult to capture the residual strength in this region. However, the number of data points is sparse and more testing of the unidirectional material is required before this conclusion can be finalized. In contrast, the cross-ply data at both stress levels displays a reduction in strength with successive cycles that can almost be classified as linear with a scatter band approximately 15% of the virgin material strength. In addition, this characteristic is not affected by the maximum stress level but simply scales according to the fatigue life.

Figure 1. Residual Strength of Unidirectional SCS6/Ti-15-3 at Selected Cycles (900 MPa Maximum Stress)

Figure 2. Residual Strength of Cross-Ply SCS6/Ti-15-3 at Selected Cycles (450 MPa Maximum Stress)

Figure 3. Residual Strength of Cross-Ply SCS6/Ti-15-3 at Selected Cycles (300 MPa Maximum Stress)

Such behavior is reasonable considering the mechanisms involved. The unidirectional specimens experience matrix relaxation within the first few cycles because the microstress in the matrix is above its yield strength of approximately 550 MPa at this temperature (427°C) [7]. A previously developed inelastic micromechanics model was employed for the present study to perform a calculation of the microstress in the matrix [8]. This analysis provided a longitudinal matrix stress of 642 MPa at the peak of the first cycle which is significantly higher than the yield stress. Thus, due to plastic/viscoplastic deformation the matrix will relax with subsequent cycles and its ability to carry load will be reduced. However, because the fibers carry the majority of the load, this will not greatly effect the overall strength of the composite. In addition, if matrix fatigue cracks develop and are bridged by the fibers, then the strength of the composite will still be maintained. It is not until some of the fibers begin to fail near this matrix crack plane that the strength of the unidirectional system will be significantly reduced. Such an effect would not be noticeable until near the end of the fatigue life [9]. The presence of fiber-bridged matrix fatigue cracks is corroborated by microscopic evaluation of a specimen polished down to the first layer of fibers (Figure 4). As this figure shows, there is no evidence of fiber damage even though a matrix fatigue crack extends through several fibers. In fact, little or no fiber cracks were observed in any of the specimens.

On the other hand, the almost linear reduction in strength observed in the cross-ply specimens can be related to the 90° plies providing a predictable mechanism for crack initiation early in the material life. It is well documented that this MMC system possesses a relatively weak fiber/matrix interface which debonds once the clamping effect of the thermal residual stresses in the matrix are overcome [1,10]. This debonding provides a source for crack formation in the 90° plies which then propagate through-the-thickness into the 0° plies [11]. Such a mechanism effectively reduces the crack initiation time to the first few cycles. Thus, strength reduction associated with this is observed early in life. Microscopic evaluation revealed these

Figure 4. Bridged Matrix Crack in Unidirectional Specimen of SCS6/Ti-15-3

fatigue cracks were bridged by the longitudinal fibers in a similar manner to what is depicted in Figure 4. In addition, multiple site initiation produces a more random distribution of cracks throughout the matrix, and hence, a more gradual reduction in strength is observed as opposed to the unidirectional specimens where a single dominant fatigue crack is the main mechanism. This conclusion is further validated by the observed modulus reduction in the cross-ply specimens. Over a ten percent reduction from the initial modulus was recorded before fatigue failure of the cross-ply while the unidirectional data only shows a drop of about three percent from the initial modulus. Figure 5 plots the modulus reduction for cross-ply specimens that failed in fatigue at both the 450 MPa and 300 MPa maximum stress levels. In the figure, the modulus is normalized with each specimen's initial modulus, and the cycle number is normalized with each specimen's respective fatigue life. At least for the cross-ply, the characteristics of modulus reduction is similar in behavior to the drop in residual strength and offers the best practical method of predicting the residual strength for this layup. However, as previously mentioned, obtaining a direct quantitative relationship is difficult (see Table 1). A more extensive test program is required before any such relationship could be outlined with confidence due to the statistical scatter in the data.

Figure 6 presents all the residual strength data on a single normalized plot. For the normalized cycles, each condition (loading and layup) was normalized with respect to its average fatigue life as measured in this study. The normalization method used for the strength was as follows

$$\text{Normalized Strength} = \frac{\sigma_{RS} - \sigma_{\max}}{\sigma_{\text{ult}} - \sigma_{\max}} \quad (1)$$

Figure 5. Normalized Modulus Throughout Life for Cross-Ply SCS6/Ti-15-3

where σ_{max} is the maximum stress of the fatigue cycle and σ_{ult} is the average ultimate strength of the virgin material as found in the present study.

A distinct advantage of the above normalization is that all the data from the layups and loading conditions considered in the present work are collapsible to a single scatter band from which a safe operating region may be gleaned. In fact, the scatter associated with this representation is no more than what is observed in the fatigue tests run under identical conditions. Also, it should be noted that the multiple points plotted in Figure 6 for the cross-ply virgin strength are not from additional experiments but due to the different maximum fatigue stress level used in Eq (1). As mentioned in the preceding paragraphs, the damage initiation mechanisms for the unidirectional versus cross-ply material are not the same. However, both systems display similar characteristics of maintaining a significant portion of their strength up to 50% of the expected life.

CONCLUSIONS

The present study examined the SCS6/Ti-15-3 titanium matrix composite for strength reduction due to tension-tension fatigue loading under isothermal conditions (427°). Both unidirectional and cross-ply layups were investigated. The unidirectional specimens exhibited damage mechanisms involving fiber-bridged matrix fatigue cracks which initiated at the surface and/or edge. Although a few small cracks were observed away from the fracture surface, a single dominant matrix crack controlled the progression of damage. Thus, due to crack ini-

tiation time and bridging fibers, the majority of strength reduction occurred near the end of expected life. More tests are required, however, to validate this finding. On the other hand, the

Figure 6. Normalized Residual Strength Versus Life for the SCS6/Ti-15-3 System

cross-ply specimens possessed a predictable crack initiation mechanism in the fiber/matrix interface of the off-axis plies. This reduced the crack initiation time, created a more random distribution of damage, and resulted in a more gradual reduction in strength throughout life than observed in the unidirectional specimens. Nevertheless, both layups maintained significant strength through 50% of the expected life.

Thus, titanium matrix composites subjected to these conditions offer the designer a robust material system. Reduction in the material's strength due to fatigue loading will not be a factor in design as long as conservative component service lives are adopted. However, further characterization with other layups and loading conditions are required before firm conclusions may be drawn.

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